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Insect Pests Constraints To Pigeonpea [*Cajanus Cajan* (L.) Millsp.] Production: Perspectives of Farmers across Benue, Kogi and Nasarawa States of Nigeria

Author Details: Aku, A.A

Department of Biology, Kaduna State College of Education Gidan Waya, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Received Date: 25-Nov-2019

Accepted Date: 06-Jan-2020

Published Date: 29-Feb-2020

Abstract

Questionnaires were administered to 225 farmers selected from three Local Government Areas of Benue, Kogi and Nasarawa States for the purpose of appraising their knowledge about the economic impact of insect pest attack on the productivity of pigeonpea. The socio-economic characteristics of the farmers were documented to see to what extent these influenced perspectives. Across the three states, the majority of the farmers were middle-aged, literate (attended and /or complete Primary, Secondary School), cultivated 1-5 hectares, and had <5years experience in Benue State and 5-10 years' experience in Kogi and Nasarawa States. Production was large to satisfy food requirement (64.0%), and secondarily for income or for the ancillary benefit of livestock feed. Nutritive value, yield, market value and adaptation to the environment were the more important determinants of varietal selection than resistance to insect pests. Insect accorded major pest status included aphids, (*Aphis craccivora*), thrips, (*Megalurothrips sjostedti*), and *Anoplocnemis curvipes*. Most respondents (70%) agreed that late sowing accentuated insect damage just as intercropping with cereal (58% of respondents). It was only in Kogi state that a respondent claimed to use insecticide for insect control. The constraints to insecticidal control were high cost (40.0%). Lack of equipment (17.0%), lack of application skill (12.0%), and non-availability of insecticides (9.3%). Farmers-participatory research on crop loss assessment is to be encouraged to provide a premise for control action against economically-important insect pests of pigeonpea in Benue, Kogi, and the Nasarawa States

Key Words: Pigeonpea, Farmer's perspective, Insect pests

INTRODUCTION

Pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan* (L.) Millsp.) is a major grain legume in many parts of the tropical regions of the world. In African cropping systems, it is grown mainly by smallholder farmers who derive multiple benefits from the crop (Odeny, 2007; Egbe and Vange, 2008; Gwata, 2010). The major benefits include improved soil fertility, food for human consumption and income generation (Amarteifio *et al.*, 2002; Shiferaw *et al.*, 2007). In Kenya, Malawi, Tanzania and Uganda, pigeonpea is consumed fresh as green vegetable beans because it is inexpensive and contains more protein and minerals than greenpea, *Pisumsativum* (Faris *et al.*, 1987). In addition pigeonpea is highly tolerant to drought making it appropriate for production; particularly in semi-arid regions of the world (Ritchie *et al.*, 2000; Silim *et al.*, 2005; Gwata and Siambi, 2009; Kumar *et al.*, 2011)

Biotic factors such as fungal diseases and insect pests are the major productivity limiting factors in many regions where pigeon pea is grown (Okeyo-Owour and Khamala, 1980; Shanower *et al.*, 1999; Minja *et al.*, 1999; Hillock *et al.*, 2000; Gwata *et al.*, 2006; Dialoke *et al.*, 2010). Grain yield is reduced by insects which attack the crop mostly at the reproductive stage, feeding on flower and pods (Minja *et al.*, 1996; Shanower *et al.*, 1999; Srilaxmi and Ravindra, 2010; Dialoke *et al.* 2012; Marimuthu *et al.* 2012; Aku and Ukwela, 2019). It is documented that pod sucking bugs mainly from Alydidae, Coreidae and Pentatomidae families have been associated with pigeonpea resulting from 50% to 75% damage (Materu, 1970; Minja, 1997). Also it has been reported that pod feeding Lepidoptera and seed feeding Diptera accounted for up to 35% and 46% yield losses, respectively in Kenya (Minja, 1997). Studies on insect pests infestation on pigeon pea in Nigeria is scanty. However, Dialoke *et al.*, in 2012, discovered *Zonocerus variegatus* E., *Helicoverpa armigera* H., *Riptortus dentipes* Fab., *Nezera viridula* L., *Clavigralla tomentosicollis*, *Anoplocnemis*

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curvipes Fab., *Mylabris pustulata* T., *Aphis crassivora*, and *Megalurothrips sjostedti* Trybon. as the dominant insect pests in Imo state. This work was designed to study the attitude and knowledge of farmers in Nasarawa, Benue and Kogi state on their pigeonpea farms in respect to insect pest infestation and damage.

MATERIAS AND METHODS

Three villages known for high hectarage pigeonpea cultivation were selected in each of Benue, Kogi, and Nasarawa state. The villages were Awume, Agadagba and Okpiko-Ehatukpe in Benue State; Kubiri, Kpandu and Edenyi in Kogi State; and Chessu, Andaha and Kanja in Nasarawa State. In each village, questionnaires (see appendix 1) were administered to 25 farmers (of both sexes) to document their knowledge of insect pest infestation and damage to the crop, awareness of the economic impact of pest infestation, and document control practices if any. In addition, socio-economic characteristics of the farmers (age, sex, education, area cultivated, farming experience, the purpose of farming etc) were documented.

DATA ANALYSIS

Non-parametric statistics (percentages) were used to identify gaps in farmers' knowledge about insect pest infestation and damage to pigeonpea and to identify the prevalent indigenous pest control tactics in use in pigeonpea production.

RESULTS

A total of two hundred and twenty five questionnaires were administered in the three states. This comprised of seventy-five in each of Benue, kogi and Nassarawa state.

The age distribution of the respondents is shown in Table 1. It shows that the age range of 51 to 60 years had the highest (26.0%) respondents. Among the three states, the highest (44.2%) respondents were in Benue state with the age range of 41 to 50. This is followed by the age range of 51 to 60 years in Nassarawa state with 39.2%. Benue state had the least percentage respondent with age greater than 60 and Kogi state with age less than 20.

Out of the total respondents, 60.2% were male while the rest (39.5%) were female. The highest (69.8%) percentage respondents were married; this is followed by widows with 24.9%. Those respondents that have not married were the least with percentage respondent of 3.2%.

Only 12.3% of the respondents were illiterates with the highest (23.8%) respondents in Nasarawa state. Those that attended secondary school had the highest (44.8%) respondents. Among the three states, Benue state had the highest (29.5%) respondents that attended a tertiary level of education while Nasarawa state was the least (3.2%).

Respondents with farming experience of less than 5 to 10 years were the highest. However, among the three states, Benue state had the highest (37.9%) percentage respondents with less than five years. The least (6.6%) percentage respondents in farming experience were in Nasarawa state with those greater than 20 years (Table 1).

Seventy one percent of the total percentage of respondents cultivated pigeonpea mainly for food, and this is cougth across all the three states. Some of the respondents used it for income and livestock feed (Table 1).

Table 2 showed farmers' perception of the effect of cultural practices on crop damage by insects. Among the respondents, 83.5% of them responded that fertilizer application reduces insect pest damage while 16.5% responded that it accentuates damage. In terms of the cropping system, 62.4% of the respondents intercropped pigeonpea with other crops while 37.6% cultivate it as a sole crop. Seventy six percent of the respondents planted pigeonpea early, whereas only a few of them plant it late. In terms of cropping pattern, 11.3% of the respondents used close spacing while only 2.6% use wide spacing with the least (1.6%)

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respondents in Kogi state. The highest (37.0%) respondents among the three states used nothing to control insect pest infestation and damage (Table 26). Some of the respondents (35.4%) said the use of a cultural method like manipulation of planting dates. Other respondents (27.1%) said the use of mechanical methods like hand picking the insects on the crop. Only 0.5% of the respondents said the use of chemical methods to control insect pests and this was only in Kogi state. The highest (43.0%) respondents could not apply the insecticides because of its high cost, while 22.6% saw it as no need for the application (Table 26). 13.6% of the respondents had no application skills. Few (9.8%) of the respondents said the insecticides were not available for them to use.

In terms of hectareage, the highest (23.4%) respondents had 2 hectares while the least (0.5%) was >5 hectares (Table 4). Among the three states, the highest percentage respondents were in Benue state with 32.1% having 2 hectares. This was followed by Nasarawa state with 28.6% having <1 hectare. Only 0.5% of the respondents had >5 hectares of pigeonpea farm and this was only in Nasarawa state. The highest (49.1%) respondents prefer the Igbongbo white variety of pigeonpea. However, there was another brown variety that they did not know the name and 39.0% of the respondents prefer it (Table 4). Food value had the highest (35.6%) respondents being the reason for their choice of variety. This was followed by high quality with 27.6%. Resistance to pest had the least respondents with 2.8%. The most common insect pests identified on the pigeonpea field in the three states were *A. curvipes*, *C. tomentosicolis*, *A. crassivora*, *M. sjostedtii*, *M. obtusa* among others. Identification was done with the help of those specimens collected and identified at A.B.U. Zaria.

Figure 9 represents the pest rating by respondents in the three states. Weed had the highest respondents followed by insects. Disease, birds and rodents were rated low by the respondents.

Discussion

The extensive cultivation of the crop in Nasarawa state (>5hectares) means that in those areas farmers have started to notice its importance either as a source of good food or income (table 1).

Most of the respondents were literate people. Those that were having tertiary education were either primary or secondary school teachers and were not full time farmers. They go to the farm only after working hours. The higher number of respondents (<5 to 10 years in farming experience) shows that the farmers were not yet fully aware of the importance of the crop in the three states. Also the low percentage of respondents with farming experience at the age of >20 years showed that farmers were not yet conversant with the crop. Most of the farmers grow the crop for food because a lot of them had not seen it as a source of income.

Most of the farmers grow the Igbongbo white variety because of its nutritive value.

The most common insect pests identified on the pigeonpea farms were consistent with those reported in the literature in Nigeria by Dialoke *et al*, 2010 and 2012.

The majority of the respondents intercrop pigeonpea with maize, millet, sorghum, and soybean ostensibly to maximally utilize land and spread risk. Reduction in pest infestation and damage occurs where a component crop serves as a decoy plant, trap crop or a physical barrier to within-field dispersion. Matterson (1982), Olufemi and Odebiyi (2001), Madang *et al.*, (2012) have shown that a component crop in a mixture sometimes reduces insect pest numbers. Amoako-Atta and Omolo (1983) and Amoako-Atta *et al* (1983) evaluated a maize-cowpea-cereal intercrop and found that the percentages of flower and pod damage by *M. vitrata* on the legume crop were consistently lower in various legume-cereal combinations than in pure stands of cowpea. Jackai (1995) had considered intercropping as an appropriate component of integrated pest management.

Late planting of pigeonpea was identified by most farmers as encouraging pest damage. This was in agreement with the report of Asante *et al* (2000) on the cowpea field that early planting of cowpea relatively suffers low infestation and damage thereby produce high yield when compared with late planting.

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The majority of the respondents were with the opinion that the application of fertilizer discourages the invasion of pigeonpea by insect pests (Table 2). These findings were in agreement with Asiwe (2009) who reported that higher rates of application of P (30 and 45 Kg P₂O₅/ha) significantly lower the infestation and damage of *A. crassivora*, *M. sjestedti*, and *M. vitrata* on cowpea. Similarly, the incidences of rice stem borers (*Scirpophaga* sp.) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) in rice fields (*Oriza sativa*) were reduced on the application of Zinc fertilizer (Mohammed, 2011).

Weed was rated highest among the pests of pigeonpea. This rating was in agreement with other authors (Hiba, *et al.*, 2013) that weed is the most destructive pest of any crop on the field.

CONCLUSION

Farmers recognized insect species as a major pest of pigeonpea and there is congruence between species designated by farmers as economically damaging and those reported in the scientific literature. Insecticidal control of pests has not been integrated into pigeonpea production practices on account of the high cost of synthetic insecticides, non -availability of the products and lack of application skills. For varietal selection, food value accorded higher priority than resistance to the pest.

Farmers-participatory research on crop loss assessment is to be encouraged to provide a premise for control action against economically-important insect pests of pigeonpea in Benue, Kogi, and the Nasarawa States.

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Table 1: Socio- Economic characteristics of pigeonpea farmers

Interviewed in Benue, Kogi and Nasarawa state in 2012 cropping season.

Parameters	% of Respondents			Mean
	Benue	Kogi	Nasarawa	
<u>Age (years)</u>				
<20	1.9	1.5	5.3	2.9
21-30	21.2	25.0	10.7	18.9
31-40	30.7	12.5	19.6	20.9
41-50	44.2	2.3	25.0	23.8
51-60	7.7	31.2	39.2	26.0
>60	1.9	9.3	10.7	7.3
<u>Sex</u>				
Male	69.8	41.5	69.2	60.2
Female	29.2	58.5	30.8	39.5
<u>Marital status</u>				
Married	66.6	60.6	76.9	69.8
Single	3.7	4.5	1.5	3.2
Divorce	13.0	13.6	3.1	9.9
Widow	35.1	21.2	18.5	24.9
<u>Educational qualification</u>				
Prim. Sch.	19.7	22.2	41.3	27.7
Sec. school	40.9	61.9	31.7	44.8
Tertiary level	29.5	12.7	3.2	15.1
No school	9.8	3.2	23.8	12.3
<u>Farming experience</u>				
<5	37.9	22.2	31.1	30.4

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6-10	31.0	26.9	32.8	30.2
11-15	13.8	22.2	18.0	18.0
16-20	27.6	20.6	11.5	19.9
>20	24.1	7.9	6.6	12.9
<u>Purpose for farming</u>				
Food	70.0	69.7	74.6	71.4
Income	20.0	28.8	23.8	24.2
Livestock	10.0	1.5	1.6	4.4

Table 2: Farmers' perception of the effect of cultural practices on pigeonpea in Benue, Kogi and Nasarawa state in 2012 cropping season

Parameters	% of Respondents			
	Benue	Kogi	Nasarawa	Mean
<u>Fertilizer application</u>				
Accretuates damage	17.0	6.6	25.9	16.5
Reduces damaged	83.0	93.4	74.1	83.5
<u>Cropping system</u>				
Pigeopea sole crop	20.7	16.9	25.8	37.6
Pigeonpea intercrop	67.2	55.4	64.5	62.4
<u>Planting dates/pattern</u>				
Early planting	8.5	4.7	10.9	8.0
Late planting	74.6	76.7	76.7	76.0
Close spacing	15.2	14.1	4.7	11.3
Wide spacing	1.7	1.6	4.7	2.6

Table 3: Preferred pest control practices and reasons for non-usage of synthetic insecticides

Parameters	% of Respondents			
	Benue	Kogi	Nasarawa	Mean
<u>Control method</u>				
Nothing	23.7	19.7	67.7	37.0
Mechanical method	22.0	51.5	7.7	27.1
Cultural method	54.2	27.3	24.6	35.4
Chemical method	0.0	1.5	0.0	0.5
<u>Reason for none application of insecticides</u>				
High cost	23.7	50.0	55.4	43.0
None availability	13.6	3.4	12.3	9.8
Lack of application skill	20.3	18.9	1.5	13.6
No need for application	32.2	17.2	18.5	22.6

Table 4: Responses in respect of hectareage cultivated and choice of a variety of pigeonpea in Benue, Kogi and Nasarawa state in 2012 cropping seasons.

Parameters	% Respondents ^a			
	Benue	Kogi	Nasarawa	Mean
<u>Farm size (ha)</u>				
<1	25.0	11.1	28.6	21.6
1	16.1	19.0	20.6	18.6
2	32.1	26.9	11.1	23.4
3	14.4	17.5	25.4	19.1
4	10.7	12.6	3.2	8.8
5	1.7	12.6	9.5	7.9
>5	0.0	0.0	1.5	0.5
<u>Preffered variety</u>				
Igbongbo white	52.0	42.2	53.1	49.1
Brown	36.0	42.2	38.8	39.0
<u>Reasons for preference</u>				
High yield	34.5	27.8	20.6	27.6
Food value	18.1	45.9	42.8	35.6
Market value	27.2	6.5	17.4	17.0
Resistance to pests	1.8	6.5	0.0	2.8
Adaptation to environment	18.1	13.1	19.0	16.7

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Fig. 9: Pests rating by respondents on pigeonpea in Benue, Kogi and Nasarawa states in 2012 cropping seasons.